

ISic0191

I.Sicily inscription 0191

Language

Latin

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

First observed walled into the front of the 'Casa del Civico Magistrato' in Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 33

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 12.5 cm

Width 24 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cn(aeus) L[---]

2. Licin[---]

3. Pom[---]

4. mo[---]

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285223

EDR 127386

EDCS 22100118

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7416 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 113

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